

1 eV GaAsSbN-based solar cells for efficient multi-junction design: Enhanced solar cell performance upon annealing

A. Gonzalo,^{a,1} L. Stanojević,^a D. Fuertes Marrón,^b A. Guzman,^a A. Hierro,^a and J. M. Ulloa^{a,*}

^a *Institute for Optoelectronic Systems and Microtechnology (ISOM), Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Avda. Complutense 30, 28040 Madrid, Spain*

^b *Instituto de Energía Solar (IES), Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Avda. Complutense 30, 28040 Madrid, Spain*

* *Corresponding author (email: jmulloa@isom.upm.es)*

In this work, we demonstrate the beneficial effect of post-growth rapid thermal annealing (RTA) on the performance of ~ 1 eV GaAsSbN-based solar cells. Different configurations of the dilute nitride material are studied: a bulk quaternary GaAsSbN layer and type-II GaAsSb/GaN superlattices (SL) with different period thickness. The RTA treatment leads in both types of structures to an enhanced external quantum efficiency (EQE) and reduced values of the dark saturation current and series resistance. The origin of these improvements is attributed to reduced densities of N and Sb-rich clusters and point defects. Remarkably, all solar cell parameters are substantially improved, this being particularly significant for the short circuit current density (J_{SC}) and power conversion efficiency (PCE), the latter with a relative enhancement as high as 500 %. The large increment of J_{SC} is an important step towards current-matching in multi-junction solar cells containing GaAsSbN structures.

KEYWORDS: *molecular beam epitaxy; GaAsSbN; multi-junction solar cells; superlattices; rapid thermal annealing; short circuit current.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The most promising lattice-matched multi-junction solar cell (MJSC) architecture requires that the sub-cell forming the third-junction has a bandgap energy close to 1 eV (Kurtz et al., 1997) in order to promote the power conversion efficiency (PCE) over 50 % (Friedman, 2010; Luque, 2011). In this sense, GaAsSbN has been recently demonstrated as a suitable material for its application in GaAs/Ge-based MJSCs. This alloy is a dilute nitride semiconductor, and therefore, experiences an anomalously high reduction of the bandgap energy with the incorporation of small amounts of N (Sabnis et al., 2012). Moreover, Sb counteracts the tensile strain caused by N in the GaAs matrix, provided the composition ratio is $[Sb] \approx 2.8 \times [N]$ (Wicaksono et al., 2005). In the case of this particular alloy, the conduction and the valence band energy offsets can be independently controlled through the N and Sb contents, respectively, which is explained by a double-band anti-crossing model (Lin et al., 2013).

~ 1 eV bulk layers of this material have already been tested for MJSCs (García et al., 2017; Gonzalo et al., 2020, 2019; Leong et al., 2016; Milanova et al., 2020; Polojärvi et al., 2016b; Tan et al., 2014, 2011; Thomas et al., 2014; Yurong et al., 2017), though the obtained solar cell

¹ *Present address: Instituto de Micro y Nanotecnología (IMN-CSIC), Isaac Newton 8, PTM, 28760, Tres Cantos (Madrid), Spain*

40 performances are still poor due to the difficulty of obtaining high-quality material. On the one
41 hand, growth problems related to the quaternary nature of the alloy arise (Harmand et al., 2002);
42 on the other hand, even a small amount of N can give rise to compositional inhomogeneities and
43 N-related defects (Aho et al., 2014; Ahsan et al., 2015; Chen et al., 2006; Dawidowski et al., 2021;
44 Kosa et al., 2018, 2016; Li et al., 2001; Polojärvi et al., 2016a; Spruytte et al., 2001; Wicaksono
45 et al., 2007), which induce carrier localization effects and introduce non-radiative recombination
46 centers. The presence of nitrogen also induces low carrier mobilities and short minority carrier
47 lifetime. REFERENCIAS DAWIDOWSKI-lower diffusion length VOLZ 204 SUKEERTI 2018
48 To reach the 1 eV bandgap energy target, relatively high N and Sb contents (slightly over 2 %
49 and 6 %, respectively) are required, so the negative impact of N on the material properties, along
50 with Sb cluster formation, become critical issues (Gonzalo et al., 2020). Recently, replacing the
51 GaAsSbN bulk layers with short period thickness GaAsSb/GaAsN type-II superlattices (SL) has
52 been demonstrated as a useful strategy to partially overcome those problems (Braza et al., 2018;
53 Gonzalo et al., 2017; Ruiz et al., 2019) and to increase the PCE (Gonzalo et al., 2020), but the
54 achieved performance is still not optimum.

55 A post-growth rapid thermal annealing (RTA) can be employed to improve the material quality
56 and optical properties of dilute nitrides, to boost their photovoltaic performance (Kim et al., 2014;
57 Miyashita et al., 2017, 2016). Typically, the crystal quality, as well as the optical properties of
58 GaAsSbN, improve after annealing (Bharatan et al., 2007; Harmand et al., 2001; Kudrawiec
59 et al., 2005; Li et al., 2005; Maros et al., 2017), which has been usually attributed to a reduction of
60 the density of N-related localized states and non-radiative recombination centers (Bharatan et al.,
61 2007; Harmand et al., 2001; Kudrawiec et al., 2005; Li et al., 2005), although reduced
62 photoluminescence after RTA has also been reported (Gonzalo et al., 2019).

63 Nevertheless, inconclusive work has been done concerning the effect of annealing directly on
64 GaAsSbN solar cell performance. Annealing temperatures of 750—800 °C have been reported
65 both to increase (Polojärvi et al., 2016b) or decrease (Gonzalo et al., 2019) the power conversion
66 efficiency (PCE) of bulk GaAsSbN solar cells (although the N and Sb contents were different in
67 those studies). Moreover, the effect of RTA on 1 eV GaAsSb/GaAsN SL solar cells has never
68 been studied. There is only a recent work in which the PCE of lower N and Sb content SL solar
69 cells was reported to decrease after RTA (Gonzalo et al., 2019).

70 In this work, we analyze the impact of RTA on the performance of three different 1 eV
71 GaAsSbN-based solar cell designs: a bulk structure and two type-II GaAsSb/GaAsN SLs with
72 different periods thickness. We find strong enhancements of the short circuit current density (J_{SC})
73 and the PCE both in bulk and SL solar cells, higher than in any other annealed GaAsSbN-based
74 solar cell reported in the literature. RTA results also in a strong reduction of the series resistance
75 (R_S) both at dark and illuminated conditions.

76 2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

77 The analyzed samples were grown by molecular beam epitaxy on GaAs (001) oriented
78 Si-doped (GaAs n+) substrates, which were outgassed before the growth process. The wafers have
79 a thickness of 250 μm . All samples are grown under As_4 overpressure conditions to avoid As
80 desorption from the sample surface, and with a growth rate of 1 ML/s. The atomic N flux is
81 provided by a RF plasma source using a 0.1 sccm flow of N_2 . The As_4 , Sb_4 and Ga are provided
82 by Kundsens effusion cells. The fluxes were monitored.

83 The general structure of the samples is presented in Fig. 1 (a). The substrate surface is annealed
84 at $\sim 620^\circ\text{C}$ for 5 minutes to desorb the native oxide layer. The first layer, a 250-nm-thick GaAs
85 Si-doped buffer layer, is deposited at $\sim 580^\circ\text{C}$. The $\sim 580^\circ\text{C}$ temperature was selected because it
86 is inside the optimal temperature range for growing high-quality GaAs. Then, the temperature is

87 reduced to $\sim 470^\circ\text{C}$, at which the undoped active layer of the sample is deposited. This $\sim 470^\circ\text{C}$
 88 temperature is optimized for the growth of N-containing samples, as it guarantees high N
 89 incorporation (Odnoblyudov et al., 2001).

90 In the first sample, the active layer consists of an 816-nm-thick GaAsSbN bulk layer (sample

FIG. 1: (a) General sketch of the sample structure and top view of one of the processed mesa-etched devices. (b) Epitaxial and expected band structure the i-GaAs(Sb)(N) layers of the three samples, that consists of a GaAsSbN bulk layer (sample bulk), a GaAsSb/GaAsN SL with 6 nm period (sample SL II-6), and a GaAsSb/GaAsN SL with 3 nm period (SL II-3).

91 *bulk*). In the second sample, the active layer is a type-II SL structure consisting of alternating
 92 3-nm-thick GaAsSb and 3-nm-thick GaAsN layers, which are repeated 136 times, so the total
 93 thickness of the active layer is 816 nm. The total period thickness is 6 nm (sample SL-II 6). The
 94 third sample active layer is also a type-II SL structure but with 1.5-nm-thick GaAsSb and
 95 1.5-nm-thick GaAsN layers. The structure is repeated 272 times, so the total 816 nm thickness of
 96 the active layer is maintained with a total period thickness of 3 nm in this case (sample SL-II 3).
 97 A sketch of the epitaxial structure of each sample as well as their expected bands structure is shown
 98 in Fig. 1 (b).

99 Bulk and both SL samples were grown using the same N and Sb fluxes, that were chosen after
 100 calibrating the composition of ternary (GaAsN and GaAsSb) alloys, corresponding to 2.3 % N
 101 and 6.2 % Sb nominal atomic contents, respectively. Therefore, only half the amount of N and Sb
 102 was used to fabricate the SLs as compared to bulk. This combination was chosen because it fulfills
 103 the lattice matching condition and allows to obtain a $\sim 1.0 \text{ eV}$ bandgap. Precise control over the
 104 opening and closing of the shutters of both Sb and N sources is essential for the correct growth of
 105 the SLs.

106 Finally, the growth temperature is raised again to 580°C to deposit a 50-nm-thick Be-doped
 107 capping layer on top. In the buffer and the capping layer, doping is applied by opening the shutters
 108 of the Si and Be elemental sources, respectively. Both n- and p- type nominal doping
 109 concentrations are $2 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. For these doping concentrations, the Si, as well as the Be doping
 110 level in GaAs, are proportional to the atoms arrival rate, so as the doping cells provide a constant
 111 flux, doping must have a regular profile (Ilegems, 1977; Neave et al., 1983). The sample
 112 configuration is, therefore, a p-i-n junction, with the active layer as the intrinsic layer.

113 A portion of each sample was annealed at 850 °C in a 30 s long RTA cycle, performed in an
114 Ulvac MILA-3000 furnace. The samples are annealed in an N₂ inert atmosphere, encapsulated
115 between two GaAs wafers. At annealing temperatures higher than 800 °C, GaAs evaporates, with
116 a preferential loss of As. The encapsulation of the sample reduces As desorption (Haynes et al.,
117 1988).

118 To structurally analyze the samples, high-resolution X-ray diffraction (HR-XRD) was
119 employed to acquire one dimensional symmetrical ω - 2θ scans around the (004) GaAs Bragg
120 reflection, acquired in an X'Pert Pro Pan'alytical diffractometer. The x-ray tube consists of a
121 tungsten cathode at 20 mA and a Cu anode operating at 45 kV with a Be window, and the emission
122 line used is the Cu-K α 1 (1.54056 Å). The incident optics count with a parabolic X-ray mirror and
123 a Ge(220) asymmetrical monochromator. X'Pert Epitaxy and Smoothfit software is employed for
124 XRD simulation and fitting.

125 After structural characterization, standard processing techniques were used to fabricate
126 200 μ m-diameter mesa-etched single-junction solar cells on both as-grown and RTA sample
127 pieces. The main fabrication process steps are: 1) ultraviolet photolithography to define the
128 pattern of the mesas on the sample surface. 2) A wet etching process using an H₃PO₄-H₂O₂-H₂O
129 (1:1:8) solution with a total etching deep of ~ 1.5 μ m to define the mesa structures. 3) Evaporation
130 of a n-type contact consisting of Au-Ge/Au (800/2000 Å) at the backside of the sample to create
131 an extended contact. 4) A second ultraviolet photolithography to define a half-moon-shaped
132 pattern over each mesa. 5) Evaporation of p-type Au/Au-Zn/Au (100/800/2000 Å) contact on top
133 of the sample. 6) A lift-off process to eliminate extra p-type metal outside the contour of the top
134 contacts. 7) A one-minute annealing cycle of the contacts at 380° C. The photolithography mask
135 aligner employed is a Karl Suss MJB3. A sketch of the final structure of one of the obtained
136 devices along with a top view of one actual 200 μ m cell can be seen in Fig. 1. The obtained
137 devices are not optimized as solar cell devices but are suitable for comparative purposes.

138 3. Analysis of the device characteristics was performed by room temperature dark
139 current-voltage (IV) and external quantum efficiency (EQE) measurements, in both cases
140 using a K2401 Keithley source meter as well as a K6514 Keithley electrometer. For the
141 EQE measurements, a QTH lamp and a 0.34 m spectrometer were employed. The EQE is
142 not a direct measurement but is extracted from photocurrent measurements after a
143 straightforward data conversion. Finally, one-sun IV characterization of the solar cells
144 under standard spectra AM1.5G conditions were obtained using an Oriel (MODELO Y
145 CLASIFICACIÓN solar simulator with sample temperature control at 25° C. RESULTS
146 AND DISCUSSION

147 3.1. Structural properties of as-grown and annealed material

148 ω - 2θ XRD scans around the (004) GaAs Bragg reflection were performed on the three samples
149 before and after RTA; the diffractograms are shown in Fig. 2. All scans are centered around the
150 33.0239° peak corresponding to GaAs diffraction. In both *bulk* sample scans (the as-grown and
151 the RTA) the second diffraction peak (located at 32.997° and 32.993°, respectively),
152 corresponding to the GaAsSbN layer, is close to the GaAs substrate peak but slightly shifted
153 toward the compressive strain region. However, in the *SL-II 6* and *SL-II 3* samples, the active
154 layer diffraction peak overlaps with the GaAs peak, so in the diffractograms, only this peak can
155 be appreciated. This means that perfect lattice-matching has been achieved during the epitaxial
156 growth of SLs structures: SLs provide better control over the incorporation of the expected N and
157 Sb contents and consequently over the target average composition than bulk samples, likely by

158 reducing clustering effects that are promoted in the quaternary material due to the simultaneous
 159 presence of N and Sb atoms in the growth front. (Gonzalo et al., 2017).

FIG. 2: HR-XRD rocking curves measured on as-grown (faded lines) and RTA (lines) samples bulk, SL-II 6 and SL-II 3. The measurements are taken in the very same sample piece before and after RTA.

160 The slight shifting of the *bulk* sample layer peak position after annealing toward a lower angle
 161 ($\Delta\omega = -0.004^\circ$) corresponds to a change in the strain f of the layer (estimated by fitting of the XRD
 162 scans of -0.006% . This difference could correspond to a 0.06% increase of the average Sb
 163 content for a constant N content; to a 0.03% reduction of the average N for a constant Sb, or to
 164 an intermediate case. In any scenario, the content modification is small compared with the average
 165 6.2% Sb and 2.3% N contents. For both SLs, the main layer peak still overlaps the GaAs peak
 166 after RTA; there is no change in sample composition. Therefore, according to XRD, layer strain
 167 and composition are not substantially modified by the annealing process.

168 3.2. In both SL samples, first-order satellite diffraction peaks arising by the diffraction from
 169 the periodic structure at both sides of the main diffraction peak are well preserved after
 170 RTA. Moreover, the FWHM of these peaks is not significantly modified after the RTA;
 171 indicating that the SL structure is not perturbed at an annealing temperature of 850°C .
 172 The interspace between satellite peaks provides a period thickness of 6.1 nm for *SL-II 6*
 173 and 2.7 nm for *SL-II 3*, that agree with the nominal values. Reduction of carrier trapping
 174 and non-radiative recombination upon annealing

175 Room-temperature EQE measurements at 0 V of a representative diode of each as-grown and
 176 RTA samples are shown in Fig. 3. The effective bandgap energies (E_{gap}) for each device, extracted
 177 from the peak of the derivative of the EQE spectra, are shown in Table 1. There is an energy
 178 blueshift after RTA in all samples (see values of ΔE_{gap} in Table 1). This is a typical effect of
 179 annealing in dilute nitrides (Kurtz et al., 2001), and particularly in GaAsSbN it is ascribed to an
 180 improvement of the composition homogeneity and a rearrangement of the
 181 second-nearest-neighbor atoms to the N atoms (As and Sb) as well as of the nitrogen pairs (Hsu
 182 et al., 2012; Lin et al., 2008). Besides this inherent effect, the blueshift can also be related to a
 183 reduction in the localization energy due to cluster dissolution and decomposition of nitrogen pairs
 184 upon annealing (Braza et al., 2018). The smaller ΔE_{gap} for both SLs in comparison with the bulk

185 points to smaller localization effects in as-grown structures, probably related to a better initial
 186 material quality (García et al., 2017). The smaller energy shift upon annealing is a potential
 187 advantage of the SLs over the bulk, as it means better control over the sub-cell bandgap energy.

188 The EQE of all the samples undergoes a significant increase after RTA, which points to an
 189 improved carrier extraction efficiency. Different factors, all related to an improved material

FIG.3: Room temperature EQE at 0 V of one solar cell of each as-grown (faded lines) and RTA (bright lines) sample: bulk, SL-II 6 and SL-II 3.

190 quality after annealing, could contribute: 1) An enhancement of the electric-field-assisted carrier
 191 collection linked to a reduction of the background doping level in the nominally intrinsic
 192 GaAsSbN layers (Miyashita et al., 2016), 2) A reduction of carrier trapping in high N or Sb
 193 content clusters (Braza et al., 2018; Ruiz et al., 2019) and 3) A reduction of non-radiative
 194 recombination in defect-related recombination centers (Polojärvi et al., 2016b). Indeed, we have
 195 recently shown that RTA reduces de density of high N and Sb content clusters in similar structures
 196 (Braza et al., 2018; Ruiz et al., 2019), which should improve the carrier diffusion length and
 197 facilitate the carrier extraction. No excluimos las otras explicaciones no?

198 Table 1: Bandgap energies (E_{gap}) of the as-grown and RTA devices, and energy blueshift (ΔE_{gap}) after
 199 annealing. The E_{gap} values are extracted from the peak of the derivative of the EQE spectra.

	E_{gap} RTA (eV)	E_{gap} as-grown (eV)	ΔE_{gap} (meV)
bulk	(1.065±0.005)	(1.000±0.005)	65±7
SL-II 6	(1.115±0.005)	(1.075±0.005)	40±7
SL-II 3	(1.120±0.005)	(1.095±0.005)	25±7

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201 The enhancement of the EQE is much larger in the *bulk* sample than in both SLs, probably due
 202 to the larger density of clusters and stronger non-radiative recombination in the as-grown *bulk*
 203 sample (Gonzalo et al., 2020), in agreement with the larger bandgap energy blueshift upon RTA.
 204 Remarkably, the *bulk* sample, having initially the lowest EQE, has the largest EQE after RTA.

205 An indication of a change in non-radiative recombination upon annealing is provided by the
 206 dark JV curves. Fig. 4 (a) shows the positive voltage part of the dark JV curves obtained from a
 207 representative device of each as-grown and RTA sample. The dark saturation current density (J_0)
 208 of the diodes can be calculated from the fit of the curves to the ideal diode equation using the
 209 PVLighthouse software (“PV lighthouse equivalent circuit calculator.

210 <https://www.pvlighthouse.com.au/equivalent-circuit,> n.d.); values are shown in Table 2. A
 211 significant reduction of J_0 is obtained for the three different structures after the annealing, which
 212 is likely linked to the reduction of the non-radiative recombination in the material. The stronger
 213 reduction of J_0 in the *bulk* structure supports the idea of the existence of a larger density of
 214 non-radiative centers in the as-grown quaternary structure than in the SLs. A strong enhancement
 215 of the shunt resistance ($R_{SH\ dark}$) of an order of magnitude is also observed in the *bulk* structure
 216 (see Table 2). Although it is not straightforward to separate the contributions of J_0 and $R_{SH\ dark}$
 217 from the fit to the diode equation, we can conclude that there is a combined improvement in both
 218 parameters after annealing in all samples. The series resistance ($R_{S\ dark}$) is significantly reduced in
 219 all cases after RTA (see Table 2).

220 The strong reduction of $R_{S\ dark}$ can be confirmed by analyzing it as a voltage-dependent
 221 parameter (more in accordance with its distributed character), instead of a fixed, voltage-
 222 independent value. The method employed consists of dividing the voltage difference between the
 223 actual dark curve and the extrapolated straight line at a certain current density by the value of
 224 such current density (Zekry and Al-Mazrou, 1996). The obtained $R_{S\ dark}$ values are shown in Fig.
 225 4 (b). The voltage range employed for the calculations spans from the point where the voltage
 226 drop starts to be significant up to the voltage where the current reaches the current limit imposed
 227 during the measurement. In all devices, $R_{S\ dark}$ decreases for increasing current. This tendency has
 228 been previously observed in the literature (Aberle et al., 1993; Breitenstein and Rißland, 2013;
 229 Fong et al., 2013; Turek, 2014) and attributed to the distributed nature of the R_S . The voltage-
 230 independent values obtained previously by fitting to the ideal diode equation agree reasonably
 231 well with the high current limit of the voltage-dependent values.

FIG.4: (a) Positive voltage region of dark JV curves of one diode of each as-grown (faded lines) and RTA (bright lines) sample: *bulk*, *SL-II 6* and *SL-II 3*. (b) Series resistance at dark conditions ($R_{S\ dark}$) as a function of the current density.

232 Table 2: Dark saturation current density (J_0), shunt resistance ($R_{SH\ dark}$), and series resistance ($R_{S\ dark}$) of
 233 the as-grown and RTA devices, extracted from the fit to the ideal diode equation.

	J_0 (mA/cm ²)		$R_{SH\ dark}$ (kΩ cm ²)		$R_{S\ dark}$ (mΩ cm ²)	
	as-grown	RTA	as-grown	RTA	as-grown	RTA
<i>bulk</i>	$2.48 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.56 \cdot 10^{-4}$	23	180 (170-250) 210+40	67	4 (3.7-4.1) 3.9+0.2
<i>SL-II 6</i>	$5.36 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.21 \cdot 10^{-4}$	120	350 (170-360)	89	39 (38.5-40.7)

				265+-95		39.6+-1.1
				270+-90		40+-1
<i>SL-II 3</i>	$5.20 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$5.30 \cdot 10^{-5}$	400	420 (360-420)	44	1 (1.0-1.2)
				390+-30		1.1+-0.1

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$R_{S \text{ dark}}$ is related to the intrinsic response of the device to the movement of current through it and includes the material resistance, the contact resistance between the metal contact and the material, and the resistance of the metal contacts. The differences between solar cells cannot be due to contact-related effects because the fabrication process was the same for all devices. Therefore, the different $R_{S \text{ dark}}$ must be attributed to differences in the internal resistance of the material itself. The as-grown *SL-II 6* device has the smallest Sb and N content fluctuations along the structure as compared with *bulk* and *SL-II 3* (Gonzalo et al., 2020). The largest $R_{S \text{ dark}}$ in the as-grown *SL-II 6* device may be due to its intrinsic structure, i.e., to the weaker electronic coupling owing to the thicker period, as predicted by quantum kinetic calculations based on non-equilibrium Green's function formalism. Indeed, while transport is quasi-ballistic for both electrons and holes in *SL-II 3*, it changes to sequential tunneling plus thermal escape for holes in *SL-II 6*, due to hole wavefunction localization in the GaAsSb layers (Gonzalo et al., 2020). The fact that $R_{S \text{ dark}}$ increases even more when the period thickness is increased to 12 nm (not shown) supports this hypothesis (Aeberhard et al., 2018).

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Comparing as-grown and RTA pairs of cells, the annealed devices present lower $R_{S \text{ dark}}$ values in all cases. For RTA *bulk* and RTA *SL-II 3* devices, the voltage drop is only significant at one point of the dark IV curves due to the imposed current limit of the instrument, so the voltage-dependent $R_{S \text{ dark}}$ could be only calculated for a single current density value. $R_{S \text{ dark}}$ decreases 97 % after annealing for such currents in both cases. For the *SL-II 6* device, $R_{S \text{ dark}}$ decreases 51—59 % for the whole range of current densities. These reductions after RTA fit well with those obtained for the voltage-independent values: 94 %, 56 %, and 97 % for *bulk*, *SL-II 6*, and *SL-II 3*, respectively.

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The $R_{S \text{ dark}}$ reduction after RTA must be attributed to changes in the resistance of the material itself. On the one hand, a reduction of carrier trapping in N and Sb-rich clusters should improve transport. On the other hand, a reduced defect density would also decrease R_S . High defect densities and trap concentrations have been previously shown to increase the R_S of p-i-n diodes (Megherbi et al., 2018). The smallest $R_{S \text{ dark}}$ reduction after RTA in *SL-II 6* should be due to the better initial composition homogeneity, as mentioned above. $R_{S \text{ dark}}$ after RTA is one order of magnitude larger in *SL-II 6* than in the other solar cells due to the different transport mechanisms for holes, as mentioned above.

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3.3. Effect of annealing on solar cell performance

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Solar cell characterization under AM1.5G standard conditions was performed on the as-grown and RTA solar cells, including a solar cell with the same epitaxial structure but bulk GaAs as the active layer, for comparison. The processed diodes have a diameter of 200 μm and are uniformly arranged in a rectangular lattice. Three to five of the best devices of each sample were tested. Fig. 5 shows the JV curves of one representative device of each sample. Comparing the performance of RTA and as-grown GaAsSbN-based devices, both J_{SC} and open-circuit voltage (V_{OC}) improve significantly after the annealing process. There is a substantial enhancement of the J_{SC} : 247 %, 72 %, and 47 % for the *bulk*, *SL-II 6*, and *SL-II 3* structures, respectively. The enhancement of the J_{SC} is directly related to the improved carrier collection efficiency and EQE. Therefore, the increment is much larger in the bulk structure than in the SLs. Remarkably, the increase of the J_{SC} is in all samples much larger than in the reference *GaAs* cell (23 %), supporting the idea that

277 the main factor behind this enhancement is related to an improved material quality in the diluted
 278 nitride layer.

279 There is also a strong enhancement of the V_{OC} after RTA: 60 %, 53 %, and 53 % for the *bulk*,
 280 *SL-II 6* and *SL-II 3* structures, respectively, while it is reduced by 5% in the *GaAs* reference cell.
 281 However, as the bandgap energy varies between cells, V_{OC} is not the proper parameter to compare
 282 the material quality of the different cells. In this sense, the open circuit bandgap-voltage offset
 283 ($W_{OC} = E_g/q - V_{oc}$) is a more useful parameter because it is almost independent of the bandgap
 284 energy (King et al., 2011). W_{OC} is noticeably reduced after RTA: 10 %, 15 %, and 18 % for the
 285 *bulk*, *SL-II 6* and *SL-II 3* structures, respectively, though it is increased in the *GaAs* reference cell.
 286 Therefore, RTA substantially improves the material quality of the high N content 1.0 eV solar
 287 cells.

288 The fill factor (FF) relative improvements (9 %, 18 %, and 21 % for the *bulk*, *SL-II 6* and
 289 *SL-II 3* structures, respectively), are likely due to a reduction of carrier recombination (as FF
 290 depends on V_{oc}), but mainly to the reduction of series resistance after annealing.

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FIG.5: IV curves under AM1.5G conditions of a representative diode of each as-grown (faded lines) and RTA (bright lines) sample: *bulk*, *SL-II 6* and *SL-II 3*, along with a *GaAs* reference sample.

296 Series resistance at illuminated conditions ($R_{S\ light}$) is usually higher than $R_{S\ dark}$ (Aberle et al.,
 297 1993; Pysch et al., 2007; Turek, 2014) which is explained by the different current flow patterns
 298 in both cases (Aberle et al., 1993). $R_{S\ light}$ accounts for effects occurring at solar cell operating
 299 conditions, so it is a more interesting parameter to characterize real solar cell devices. A simple
 300 method described in detail in ref. 45 allows estimating $R_{S\ light}$ at a current density corresponding
 301 to the ideal operating point of the device (the one where the power provided by the cell is
 302 maximum, or maximum power point) by comparing the AM1.5G curves with the dark IV curves.
 303 The obtained $R_{S\ light}$ values for each cell are presented in Table 3. $R_{S\ light}$ values are considerably
 304 higher than the $R_{S\ dark}$ calculated from the dark IV curves, as expected. However, as happened for
 305 $R_{S\ dark}$, $R_{S\ light}$ is considerably reduced in all cases upon annealing: 43 %, 32 %, and 53 % for the
 306 *bulk*, *SL-II 6* and *SL-II 3* structures, respectively. Again, this reduction is larger for both *bulk* and
 307 *SL-II 3* structures than for *SL-II 6*, whose $R_{S\ light}$ is the highest both before and after RTA for the
 308 reasons mentioned above. Remarkably, this result is opposite to that of ref. 11, in which the slope
 309 of the illuminated IV curves in the voltage region near V_{oc} seems to increase after annealing.

310 Table 3: Series resistance at illuminated conditions ($R_{S\ light}$) of the as-grown and RTA devices.

	$R_{S\ light}$ as-grown ($\Omega\ cm^2$)	$R_{S\ light}$ RTA ($\Omega\ cm^2$)
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<i>bulk</i>	6.15 5+-2	3.45 3.4+-0.4
<i>SL-II 6</i>	9.96 11+-2	6.78 6.8+-0.5
<i>SL-II 3</i>	8.45 8+-1	3.99 3.9+-0,4
<i>GaAs</i>	2.49 (((3+-1)))	4.62 (((4.8+-0.3)))

311

312 The fact that the evolution of $R_{S \text{ light}}$ with RTA is the opposite in the GaAs reference cell
313 supports the idea that changes are not contact-related, but due to modified material properties.
314 The composition homogenization and reduction of defect density after RTA happening in the
315 dilute nitride layers does not take place in GaAs, in which, in agreement with the reduced V_{oc} ,
316 recombination could be increasing after RTA.

317 Finally, the relative PCE improvements are 503 %, 183 %, and 170 % for the *bulk*, *SL-II 6*,
318 and *SL-II 3* structures, respectively. The much larger improvement in the *bulk* sample could be
319 related to the worse initial situation regarding material quality and solar cell performance, in
320 agreement with the results of EQE and dark IV measurements. These PCE improvements after
321 annealing are much higher than the ones reported previously for GaAsSbN bulk solar cells in the
322 literature: 49 % in cells with similar N and Sb contents (Polojärvi et al., 2016b), and a degradation
323 of 5 % in solar cells with lower N and Sb contents (Gonzalo et al., 2019). Moreover, the only
324 study on the effect of RTA on GaAsSb/GaAsN SL solar cells showed reduced PCE after RTA
325 due to a strong reduction of the J_{sc} (Gonzalo et al., 2019). The solar cells in that study had lower
326 N contents and the J_{sc} values were already high for as-grown cells (Gonzalo et al., 2019).
327 Therefore, there are substantial differences in the effect of RTA on low and high N-content
328 GaAsSbN solar cells, which have not been considered up to now. RTA might only be beneficial
329 for solar cells with N contents above a certain value in the range of ~ 2 %.

330 Focusing on the annealed devices, all their average solar cell characteristic values are shown
331 in Table 4. It is important to note that the solar cell structure is not optimized, so relatively poor
332 performance can be expected (see the values of the GaAs cell as a reference). On the one hand,
333 the *bulk* RTA solar cell has the best J_{sc} . On the other hand, the largest V_{oc} is achieved by the
334 *SL-II 3* RTA device, which also shows the best FF. The W_{oc} values are smaller in both SL solar
335 cells than in the *bulk* and annealed *GaAs* cells. In fact, the W_{oc} of sample *SL-II 3* RTA is equal to
336 that of the *GaAs* as-grown solar cell (0.63 V). Therefore, material quality after annealing in the
337 dilute nitride SL-based solar cells is similar to that in the equivalent *GaAs* cell, which is a
338 significant achievement. The best PCE is shown by the *SL-II 3* RTA solar cell, but the value is
339 very similar to the *bulk* RTA sample because of the very large enhancement of the latter upon
340 annealing.

341 *Table 4: Average values of the solar cell characteristic parameters of several diodes of each sample after*
342 *RTA.*

	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	V_{oc} (V)	W_{oc} (V)	FF (%)	PCE (%)
<i>bulk RTA</i>	(17±1)	(0.40±0.01)	(0.67±0.01)	(61±1)	(4.1±0.2)
<i>SL-II 6 RTA</i>	(11±2)	(0.46±0.02)	(0.65±0.01)	(59±4)	(2.8±0.4)
<i>SL-II 3 RTA</i>	(14±2)	(0.49±0.01)	(0.63±0.01)	(64±2)	(4.3±0.5)
<i>GaAs RTA</i>	(18±2)	(0.74±0.01)	(0.68±0.01)	(76±1)	(10.3±0.9)

343

344 4. CONCLUSIONS

345 In conclusion, the application of a RTA cycle to GaAsSbN-based solar cells with ~ 1.0 eV
346 bandgap improves the J_{SC} , V_{OC} , and FF significantly. As a result of this, relative improvements of
347 the PCE as high as 503 % are obtained. The enhanced EQE and R_{SH} , as well as the reduced J_0 and
348 R_S , point towards reduced carrier trapping in clusters and non-radiative recombination at point
349 defects after RTA. The large increase of the J_{SC} after RTA is particularly relevant since it could
350 help current matching when integrating these cells into a MJSC device. Therefore, these results
351 represent an important step towards the integration of GaAsSb/GaAsN SLs in GaAs/Ge-based
352 MJSC.

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